

Effect of Laboratory and Collaborative Teaching Strategies on Senior Secondary School Students' Achievement and Retention in Geometry in Port Harcourt Local Government Area, Rivers State.

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Abstract

The study determined the effect of laboratory and collaborative teaching strategies on senior secondary school students' achievement and retention in geometry in Port Harcourt Local Government Area, Rivers State. The study adopted a quasi-experimental design, guided by two research questions and two hypotheses. The population of the study comprised 7,719 SS2 students; four secondary schools were randomly selected, two of the schools were assigned as control group while the other two was also assigned as the experimental group, a sample of 254 SS2 students were used in their intact class. The instrument used for the study was Circle Theory Instructional Package (CTIP); a well-designed lesson note constructed based on laboratory and collaboration teaching method. Descriptive statistics of mean and Standard Deviation were used to answer the research questions while the hypotheses were tested using ANCOVA at 0.05 level of significance. ANCOVA was used because it will adjust for individual differences in the covariate, reduced the error term and providing a more precise estimate of the treatment effect. The findings of the study revealed that achievement and retention of students taught geometry using laboratory and collaborative teaching strategies improved than students taught using conventional method; Based on the findings it was recommended that serving teachers of mathematics should adopt the use of laboratory and collaborative strategies in the teaching of mathematics. Curriculum planners should revise mathematics curriculum to include the use of teaching strategies that will help students to understand, retain and be able to apply conceptual knowledge in solving novelty problems.

Keywords: Laboratory, Collaborative Teaching Strategies, Performance, Retention and Circle theory.

Introduction

In Nigeria Mathematics is an important subject at all levels; primary, secondary and tertiary. Mathematics practice is as old as the world, from the beginning to recent civilization and development in science and technology. In all these, mathematics has been the corner stone. It is one subject that cut across all subjects and fields of life. Neglecting mathematics means bring to a halt one's breathing. This is because it is only a dead man that does not practice mathematics. The application of mathematics knowledge in our daily lives is inevitable, because it is part of human life. Chand, et al (2021) opined that mathematics education is the foundation of scientific and

technological knowledge that contributes significantly towards the socioeconomic development of a nation. It is of this accord that all nations consider mathematics as a core subject with great attention attributed to it.

Bah (2021) described the poor performance found among senior secondary school students in mathematics at both internal and external examination to be quite discouraging and unappealing and requires urgent attention; the causes as revealed in his study are teachers teaching methods, language competence, poor teaching and learning materials, parents and family members, schools policies, society, infrastructure and government. Varaidzaimakondo and Makondo (2020) attributed the causes of poor performance among senior students in Mathematics to be lack of qualified teachers, lack of teaching and learning resources, math phobia, improper teaching methods, anxiety, and overcrowded classrooms.

Teaching is a process of transmitting knowledge and ideas into learners, bringing about desirable changes anchored on the achievement of specific objectives of learning and the achievement of learning objectives depends solely on the process or method. According to Wonu and Zalmon, (2017) learning occurs as a result of total adaptation resulting from good assimilation and accommodation of concept taught; students thereafter apply the accommodated knowledge of concepts in solving related mathematics problems. Therefore, partial or no accommodation of concept learnt results into poor performance. The aforementioned justifies the need for teachers to adopt teaching approaches and strategies that enhance student understanding and retention. Rabi, Jamila and Mukhtar (2017) opined that the recent shift from teacher centered approach to student centered approach is the reason why teachers should focus on the application of teaching strategies that will foster understanding and better comprehension of science and mathematics concepts. In their studies, they further explained that teaching strategies adopted by mathematics teachers at both primary and secondary levels should be one that promotes active learning by providing learners' guided constant practice of concept taught for effective retention with a resultant effect in their achievement. Hence, based on current accepted mathematics teaching approach, it is paramount that teaching strategies applied by teachers should be one that will help students understand, comprehend, recall and apply conceptual knowledge in problem solving. According to Bala (2018), inability of students to retain what they have learnt, has been identified as one of the contributing factor to students poor performance in Science subjects; this is because retention plays a major role in the application of scientific concepts, knowledge and skills in solving problems.

Ejiofor-Chima and Mumuni (2019) defined retention as the ability of students in remembering or application of knowledge base in solving problems in geometry. It is the ability to recall gained knowledge, retrieve perceived ideas, remember and recognize concept learnt in solving problems. Therefore, understanding is connected to retention and in the same chain it results into good performance. Man has limited capacity to memorize, to correctly and effectively use or apply whatever he has learnt. Hence, when teachers present mathematics concepts in abstraction, students will not be able to retain what they have learnt. Therefore, it is important that teachers

should present mathematics concepts using instructional strategies that promote understanding, retention and application for an improved performance.

Mathematics is one subject that students perceive to be difficult due to its abstract nature. Its teaching requires the use of methods/strategies that transform the abstractness into reality, reduces math-phobia, improves students' proficiency, encourage problem solving through mastery of concepts, creativity skills and love for the subject by presenting it using familiar life experience and hands on activities. (Charles-Ogan, 2014). The teaching methods/strategies should emphasize conceptual understanding that builds critical thinking and logical reasoning which are applied in deducing solutions to problems that result into competence. Ado and Abasi (2014), posited that practical work provides the most effective means by which understanding and application of mathematics concepts can be improved. It enables students to see mathematics ideas which are contained within the various activities, thus making the learners to become critical thinkers. In respect of the aforementioned, learners are guided to discover knowledge and understand concept through appropriate activities that encourage them to plan patterns in mathematics; leading to rules, formula and stimulating learning situation. According to old Chinese proverb which informs us; I hear and forget; I see and remember; I do and I understand. This tends to support the use of laboratory method in enhancing students understanding, retention and application.

Charles-Owaba (2019) disclosed that laboratory strategy is one teaching method that enhances students understanding of basic mathematics principles, theorems, definitions, mathematical skills acquisition and development of good learning habits like self-esteem, confidence, problem solving, creative mind, spirit of scientific thinking and cooperation through complex interaction. The understanding of geometric concepts is anchored on manipulation of materials, which justifies laboratory method to be appropriate for its teaching. Laboratory method actively engages learners' mentally, physically and promotes understanding through active engagement on activities that encourages material interaction. Smith et al (2017) defined collaborative method as team learning that encourages individuals in a small group to critically think, reason and work together on activities or learning task or solve problems of which ensures that everyone participates. Collaborative learning is an interactive process that takes place among groups or individuals of similar characteristic with different learning abilities. During the interactive process of collaborative learning weaker students tends to improve as most the concepts are broken down in a simple understandable language by their peers and also students learn with a more relaxed mind. Collaborative learning helps students in recognizing their knowledge through elaborate explanations that promote understanding and retention in their cause of social interaction, (Omenka, Kyeleve & Tali 2018).

Geometry is a branch of mathematics concerned with questions of shapes, sizes, relative positions of figures and the properties of space. The formation of shapes is as a result of the use of geometrical forms. Its knowledge is applied in all fields of life - surveying, architecture, engineering, music, navigation, astronomy, medicine (geometric imaging), psychology, philosophy and science. Ubi and Igiri (2018) in their studies identified geometry as that important

part of mathematics that students experience difficulties and suggest the application of effective teaching method along with instructional materials to derive a better understanding of the concept. The poor achievement of students in geometry, precisely circle geometry is the reason for this study and geometry been a mathematical concept that requires practical demand the need for laboratory and collaborative strategies.

Statement of Problem

The aim of Mathematics education is to achieve its set goals, which is good performance of students in both internal and external examinations; but currently, the attainment of this goal becomes a mirage of which one may ask what should be the cause. Bala (2018) explained that teaching methodology should be the major cause of students poor performance in science subjects, as most teachers still prefer using the “chalk and talk method i.e. the conventional method. Bah (2021) attributed the cause of poor performance in mathematics to be the use of inappropriate instructional strategies by Mathematics teachers. In the same manner the chief Examiners’ Report of Candidates’ Weaknesses in WAEC (2015 & 2017) identified circle theorem and plain geometry as one aspect of mathematics students experience poor performance of which is a contributory factor to students overall poor performance in mathematics. It was also ascertained by Charles-Ogan (2014) in her studies that the cause of students poor performance in mathematics is attributed to teaching methodology. This necessitates the need for this study following how important geometrical knowledge and skills are to man. The most interesting thing about geometry is that, nature speaks geometry. Thus, its knowledge and skills are important for an individual to function effectively in our world today as most of our daily activities of life require geometrical knowledge. Therefore, this study tends to identify the appropriate instructional strategy that enhances the understanding, retention and application of geometric knowledge in problem solving.

Aim and Objectives of the study

The aim of this study is to determine the effects of Laboratory and collaborative strategies on senior secondary school students’ performance and retention in geometry in Port Harcourt, Rivers State. The specific objectives of this study are to:

1. Determine the difference in mean achievement scores of students taught with Circle using laboratory and collaborative strategies and those taught using conventional method.
2. Determine the difference in mean retention scores of students taught geometry using laboratory and collaborative strategies and those taught using conventional method.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught with circle theory using laboratory and collaborative strategies and those taught using conventional method.
2. What is the difference in the mean retention scores of students taught circle theory using laboratory and collaboration strategies and those taught using conventional method?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 significant level:

H01: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught circle theory using laboratory and collaboration strategies and those taught using conventional method.

H02: There is no significant difference in the mean retention scores of students taught circle theory using laboratory and collaboration strategies and those taught using conventional method.

Methods and Materials

The design of the study was quasi experimental; pre-test and post-test method. The population of the study was 7,719 public senior secondary school two students in Port Harcourt Local Government Area of Rivers State. Four co-educational schools were randomly selected for the experimental and control groups. The sample size for the study was 254 students consisting (127) students for the experimental group; made up of two schools of 66 and 67 students. Two schools were also used for the control group, each consisting of 64 and 63 students making a total of 127 students. The classes were used in their intact nature. The instrument used for the study was Circle Theory Instructional Package (CTIP); a well-designed lesson note constructed based on laboratory and collaboration teaching method. The students in the experimental group were grouped in six to encourage collaboration and practical practice. The control group students were taught using conventional method. The standardize test used was Geometry Achievement Test (GAT) which comprises two parts: Part I gathered personal data, while Part II consisted of 40 items covering chord property, arc theorem, semi-circle theorem, segment theorem, cyclic quadrilateral theorem, and alternate segment theorem. These items were aligned with the SS2 scheme of work in the mathematics senior secondary school curriculum by NERDC 2015. The GAT questions were formulated using WAEC past questions from 2010-2019, employing a multiple-choice objective format with four options (A, B, C, and D). Each correctly answered question earned one mark, resulting in a total of 40 marks for the test. The Geometry Achievement Test (GAT) was administered after three weeks lesson to both groups to determine change in achievement. The same test Geometry Retention Test(GRT) was administered to experimental group two weeks later to determine retention difference. The reliability of GAT was established using Kuder-Richardson-20 and a coefficient of 0.79 was obtained and considered appropriate for the study. The GRT consists of two sections. Section A sought general information about respondents, while Section B bothered about their retention in geometry. The instruments were validated by two (2) mathematics educators in the Science Education Department and one (1) measurement and evaluation expert. The reliability index of the GRT was established using the Cronbach Alpha reliability estimate. Cronbach alpha was used because the GRT items were polytomously scored. The reliability index was found to be 0.80. Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) software version 26 was used to analyze the data. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation and the research hypotheses were analyzed using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) at 0.05 level of significance. ANCOVA was used because it will adjust for individual

differences in the covariate, reduced the error term and providing a more precise estimate of the treatment effect.

Results

What is the difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught geometry using laboratory and collaboration strategies and those taught using conventional method?

Table 1: Mean Achievement Scores, Standard Deviations and Mean Gain of Students Taught Using BIS and Lecture Method

Groups	N	Pre-Gat		Post-Gat		Mean Gain
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
Experimental	130	5.91	2.90	26.63	6.57	20.72
Control	124	7.52	3.63	17.90	3.96	10.33

The table above shows that the experimental group obtained a mean achievement score of 5.91 and a standard deviation of 2.90 in the Pre-GAT a mean achievement score of 26.63 and a standard deviation of 6.57 in the Post-GAT. It was also revealed that the control group which represents those taught with the conventional method obtained a mean achievement score of 7.52 and a standard deviation of 3.63 in the Pre-GAT and a mean achievement score of 17.90 and a standard deviation of 3.96 in the Post-GAT. The standard deviations of students taught geometry using LCS and conventional methods increased from pre-GAT to post-GAT indicating that the scattering of the scores increases as the mean increased. The scattering of the scores was higher for those taught geometry using LCS when compared to those taught geometry using the conventional method. The mean gain between Pre-GAT and Post-GAT for experimental and control groups are 20.72 and 10.33 respectively. This implies that students taught geometry using the LCS had a higher mean gain when compared with those taught using the lecture method.

What is the difference in the mean retention scores of students taught geometry using laboratory and collaboration strategies and those taught using conventional method?

Table 2: Mean Interest Scores, Standard Deviations and Mean Gain of Students Taught Using LCM and Lecture Method

Groups	N	Pre-GRT		Post-GRT		Mean Gain
		\bar{x}	SD	\bar{x}	SD	
Experimental	130	1.77	0.66	3.26	1.04	1.49
Control	124	1.72	1.55	2.31	0.76	0.59

The result in Table 2 shows that the students in the experimental group had a mean retention score of 1.77 and a standard deviation of 0.66 in the Pre-GRT. In contrast, students in the control group had a mean retention score and standard deviation of 1.72 and 1.55, respectively. Similarly, in Post-GRT, the mean retention score was 3.26 and the standard deviation was 1.04 for students in the experimental group, respectively, while the mean retention score and standard deviation of students in the control group were 2.31 and 0.76, respectively. The standard deviations of students taught geometry using LCS increased from pre-GRT to post-GRT, indicating that the scattering of the scores increased as the mean increased, while the students taught with conventional method

decreased from pre-GRT to post-GRT indicating that the scattering of the scores decreased as the mean increased. The scattering of the scores was higher for those taught geometry using LCS when compared to those taught geometry using the conventional method. The mean retention gains between Pre-GRT and Post-GRT for students taught in the experimental and control groups are 1.49 and 0.59, respectively. This implies that the mean retention gains of students taught geometry using LCS was higher than those taught using the conventional method.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught geometry using laboratory and collaboration strategies and those taught using conventional method.

Table 3: Summary of Analysis of Covariance on Experimental and Control Group over achievement

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	3500.785 ^a	2	1750.392	61.229	.000	.410
Intercept	14945.017	1	14945.017	522.781	.000	.748
PREGAT	90.550	1	90.550	3.167	.077	.018
GROUP	3479.330	1	3479.330	121.708	.000	.409
Error	5031.405	176	28.588			
Total	95962.000	179				
Corrected Total	8532.190	178				

Source: Fieldwork, 2024

The summary of data analysis presented in Table 3 shows that the main effect, the teaching method has an F-calculated value of 121.708 and a p-value of 0.00 which is less than the critical p-value of 0.05. This is based on 1 degree of freedom for the numerator and 176 degrees of freedom for the denominator. Thus, the null hypothesis is not accepted; proving that there is a significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught geometry using the Laboratory and collaborative strategies and those taught using conventional method.

H02: There is no significant difference in the mean retention scores of students taught geometry using laboratory and collaboration strategies and those taught using conventional method.

Table 4: Analysis of Covariance for Students’ Mean retention Scores by Laboratory and Collaborative Strategies and lecture method

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	149.020 ^a	2	74.510	91.168	.000	.509
Intercept	310.434	1	310.434	379.839	.000	.683
PREGII	.087	1	.087	.106	.745	.001
GROUP	148.501	1	148.501	181.702	.000	.508
Error	143.841	176	.817			
Total	1245.760	179				
Corrected Total	292.861	178				

Source: Fieldwork (2024)

The summary of data analysis presented in Table 4 shows that the main effect, the teaching approach has an F-calculated value of 181.702 and a p-value of 0.00 which is less than the critical p-value of 0.05. This is based on 1 degree of freedom for the numerator and 176 degrees of freedom for the denominator. This implies that the null hypothesis is rejected. That is the difference in mean retention scores of students taught geometry, using laboratory and collaborative strategy and those taught using the conventional method is statistically significant. The table show that the intervention had a partial eta square value of 50.8% (0.508).

Discussion

Achievement and Teaching Strategies

Table 1 and 3 of the study proved that laboratory and collaborative strategies are good for the teaching/learning of geometry, as performance of experimental group was better than that of the control group. The study revealed that there is a significant improvement in the performance of students taught geometry using laboratory and collaborative strategies. This is because the two strategies enhance students understanding of concepts at a more stable state of mind. Also learning was student centered as students were allowed to explore and derive meanings themselves. Learning using the two strategies employs the use of major sensory organs for learning; thereby, fostering retention. The findings are in agreement with the study of Charles-Owaba, (2020) that students’ performance improved in geometry when they are taught with laboratory approach; also that the instructional package is not gender biased. Fima (2017), in his study proved that the teaching of trigonometry using laboratory and problem base strategies has a positive influence on students’ performance which is in line with the study. Also supported of the study was the work of Chales-Ogan, (2014), confirming improved performance on mathematics using collaborative and problem base strategies. The study also agrees with the study of Jonah and Dogo (2019), that collaborative strategy is effective in the teaching of geometry for upper basic two students. The findings are also in line with the study of Ahumaraeze and Ekwueme (2019), that constructivist

based instructional strategy, which laboratory is part of, enhance students' performance in mathematics

Retention and Teaching strategies.

The analyses result of table 2 and 4 proved that students' retentive level in geometry can be improved using laboratory and collaborative strategies; as the study revealed that there is no significant difference in the retention level of students taught geometry using laboratory and collaborative strategies. This is supported by Fima (2017), in his study proved the use of laboratory teaching strategy good for students' retention in trigonometry and Awaja (2015), also proved that collaborative and problem base strategies improve students' retention.

Conclusion.

It was established from the study that laboratory and collaboration teaching strategies enhance students' performance and retention in geometry.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Serving teachers of Mathematics should adopt the use of laboratory and collaborative strategies in the teaching of Mathematics.
2. Curriculum planners should revise Mathematics curriculum to include the use of teaching strategies that help students to understand, retain and be able to apply conceptual knowledge in solving novelty problems.
3. Teachers should be encouraged to attend workshops, seminars and conferences to acquire more knowledge on how to achieve effective teaching.

References

- Abakpa, B.O. & Folorunso, D. O. (2013). Effect of mastery learning approaches on senior secondary school students' achievement and interest in geometry in Makurdi, Benue State, Nigeria, *Abacus: The journal of the Mathematical Association of Nigeria*, 38(1), 163-176.
- Ado, I. B. & Abasi, A. U. (2014). Effect of practical approach on basic 7 mathematics students interest and performance in fraction in Uyo, Akwa Ibom State of Nigeria. *Journal of Education and Practice*, 28(5), 121-130.
- Ahumaraeze, O. U. & Ekwueme, C. O. (2019). Effect of constructivist based instructional strategy on senior secondary school students' academic performance in mathematics in Rivers State, Nigeria. *Abacus: Journal of Mathematical Association of Nigeria (MAN)*, 44(1), 219-230.
- Anigbo, L. C. & Ndukwe, J. C. (2019). Effect of constructivist instructional model on senior secondary school students' achievement in mathematics, Enugu State. *Abacus: Journal of Mathematics Association of Nigeria (MAN)*, 44(1), 166-175.
- Awaja, J. (2015). *Gender differences in mathematics achievement and retention using collaborative and problem base strategies in Abia State Nigeria*. (Unpublished doctoral dissertation), Abia State University, Nigeria.

- Bah, Y. M. (2022). Poor performance in mathematics among senior secondary school students: Lesson for education planner. *International Journal of Advance Research in Education and Literature*, volume 7/ issue-11, Doi: <http://doi.org/10.53555nnel.v7i11.968>.
- Bala, S. S. (2018). Gender Effect on Performance and Retention in Basic Science through Computer Assisted Instructional among Secondary School Students in Kano Metropolis. 59th Annual Conference Proceedings of Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN).
- Charles-Ogan, G. (2014). Mathematics laboratory and students' conception of mensuration using collaborative approaches in Rivers State. *Journal of International Academic Research for Multidisciplinary*, 2(7), 245-257.
- Charles-Owaba, T. & Abuge, M. (2020). Teachers' Perception on the Use of Mathematics Laboratory in Teaching Mathematics in Secondary Schools in Yenagoa LGA of Bayelsa State". *ABACUS, Journal of MAN*, 45(1), 20-32.
- Charles-Owaba, T. (2019). Examining Teachers' Perception on the Influence of Globalization in the Teaching and Learning of Mathematics in Secondary Schools in Yenagoa LGA of Bayelsa State. Proceedings of September, 2019, 56th Annual National Conference, 731-736.
- Ejiofor-Chima, N. A. & Mumuni, A. A. (2019) Diagnosis and remediation of learning difficulties on students' performance in geometry in Rivers State. *International Journal of Advance Educational Research*, 4(2); 43-49.
- Fima, Z. (2017). Laboratory and problem base instructional strategies on students' performance and retention in trigonometry in Abia state Nigeria. *American Journal of Educational Research*, 5(7), 717-724.
- Haruna, I. (2014). Mathematics education national development values and socio-cultural context of Nigeria. *International journal of Novel Research in Educational and Learning*.
- Ifamuyiwa, A. S & Ajilogba, S.I. (2012) A problem solving model as a strategy for improving secondary school students' achievement and retention in further mathematics. *ARNP Journal of Science and Technology*, 2(2), 2225-7217.
- Jonah, D. T. & Dogo, P. (2019). Effect of Collaborative Learning Approach on Upper Basic Two Students Interest in Geometry in Pankshin Education Zone. *Paper presented at the proceedings of 56th Annual Conference of Mathematical Association of Nigeria (MAN) Port Harcourt, September (pp 444-455)*.
- Kalu, K. C. (2015). *Group/Collaboration and discussion strategies and academic performance of students in large Biology class of senior secondary school students in Owerri Municipal (unpublished Doctoral Dissertation, Imo State University)*.
- Kurumeh, M. S., Onah F. O. & Mohammed A. S. (2012). Improving students' retention in junior secondary school statistics using the ethno-mathematics teaching approach in Obi and Oju local government areas of Benue State, Nigeria. *Greener Journal of Educational Research*, 2(3), 054-062.
- Muhammed, S. & Ibrahim, M. (2014). Influence of laboratory activities and peer-tutoring on slow learners' achievement and retention in senior secondary school trigonometry, kebbi state Nigeria. *International Journal of Advance research, IJOAR. Org 2(12) online: ISSN 2320-9143*.
- Ogunfowote, O. & Asanre, A. (2019). Effect of integrative teaching approach on students' academic achievement in secondary school mathematics. *Abacus: The journal of the Mathematical Association of Nigeria*, 44(1), 176-179.

- Olaywmi, S. O. (2022). Effects of laboratory instructional strategies on senior secondary school students geometrical performance in mathematics in Ekiti State. *Journal of Research in Science Education* vol 1, No 1(pp 194-204).
- Omenka, J. E., Kyeleve, J. I. & Tali, D. J. (2018). Effect of collaborative learning approach on upper basic two students' achievement and interest in geometry in Plateau, Abacus: *The journal of Mathematical Association of Nigeria (MAN)*, 43(1); 347-359.
- Onwuka, P. I. (2015). Effect of constructivist based instructional strategy on students learning outcome in mathematics. *Abacus: Journal of Mathematical Association of Nigeria (MAN)*, 40(1), 310-316.
- Rabiu, A. T., Jamilu, A. A., & Mukhtar, N. (2017). Effect of guided discovery method of teaching on retention and performance in geometry among senior secondary student two in Zaria local government of kaduna State Nigeria. *Abacus: Journal of Mathematical Association of Nigeria*, 42(2), 183 -192.
- Sani, S. & Salahudeen, B. (2016). Effects of geoboard and geographical globe on senior secondary school students' performance in mathematics in kaduna State. *Journal of Science, Technology & Education (JOSTE)*, 4 (1), 2277-0011
- Smith, J., Johnson, L. & Smith, J. (2017). The impart of collaborative learning on gender differences in mathematics performance: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 109(30), 369-385.
- Sule, S. S. (2018). Examination of causes and effects of anxiety on secondary school students poor academic performance in mathematics. *International Journal of Academic Research in Education*, 1-6. <http://doi.org/10.17985/ijare.398823>.
- Ubi, E. E. & Igiri, I. O. (2018). Geometry viewed as a difficult mathematics. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*, ISSN NO. 2456-2165.
- Umar Sa'ad, T., Abba, A. & Abdullahi, M. S. (2014). The Causes of Poor Performance in Mathematics among Public Senior Secondary School Students in Azare Metropolis of Bauchi State. *IOSR Journal of Research & Method in Education (IOSR-JRME)*, (4),7 32-40 www.iosrjournals.org
- Varaidzaimakonda, P & Makondo, D. (2020). Causes of poor academic performance in mathematics at ordinary level; A case of Mavuzani High School, Zimbabwe. [www.ijhssi.org/volume 9 Issue 6 Ser.I/june 2020/pp10-18](http://www.ijhssi.org/volume%209%20Issue%206%20Ser.I/june%202020/pp10-18).
- West African Examination Council. Chief Examiners' Annual Report (2015-2017). Lagos: WAEC. Retrieved on 17th June, 2018 from [http://www.waecgh.org>portals.PDF](http://www.waecgh.org/portals/PDF).
- Wonu, N., & Zalmon, I. (2017). Diagnosis and remediation of senior secondary students common learning difficulties in mathematics. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Education science*, 5(1), 256-282.